

Clinical trial Phase - IV For Brain Tumors Based Nanodrugs Via Advanced Molecular Biology & Molecular Neurosurgery Levels a Theory Of gene Engineering Technology {a clues For New Drug}

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Abstract: The ebv have been made two clinical trials in neurooncology based 1-gene therapy 2-neurosurgery molecular PET since the ebv have been built 2 powerful phenomenons which are; tocagen self powered by c-group and self powered by p-group in a recommendatitions of cis/trans helix loop helix phenomenon of cis/trans carboxyl group based helix loop helix by phosphate group trans in issue based p-group and cis in issue based c-group.

The nitrogenous base (A & G) fully forms the ebv gene seven in one to six ribosomes for a trans proteins subunit like phenylalanine and tyrosine based covalent and ionic bonds in its shape and a Brilliant form.

Keywords: ebv (Epstein Barr Virus); tocagen toca 511 and toca FC (5-fluorocytosine prodrug of 5-fluorouracil); P-group & C-group; brain tumors (GBM & MB); Molecular Imagiings (MRI & PET).

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years tocagen achieved a powerful fully treated clinical trials in neuro oncology, GBM it depends on 5-fluorocytosine prodrug of 5-fluorouracil ((Toca 511 and Toca FC)).

2. MATERIAL & METHODS

1-ebv gene 7:-

the ebv gene 7 is harmful gene or an a cancerous gene used to distroyed helicase gene when we add a P-group cis/trans helix loop helix with carbon isoforms (bentiomars); the ebv gene 7 is clinically fully estimated as a tool of gene editing crispr/cas9 cre(ebv) Lox(helix loop helix) in its shape and uniform without Medullooblongata (MO).of tissues based microarryes ; the form of Medullooblongata (MO) In ebv is powerful mosiac dropples spongy fish with ultra- PET imaging 5- fluorouracile of amino acids in its helicase helix loop helix uniform; the ebv gene 7 is and Arc with its shape helix loop helix with cis P-group and trans with C-group.

2- GBM Samples:-

six of seven were fixwd for clinical trial phase- IV; Study they do elven of out 2 patiants with 5- Fluorouracil prodrug Toca 511 TocaFC; Five pataints injected with ebv gene 7 cis/trans P & C Groups editing of catalase enzyme from GBM pataints by powerful tool or technology Crispr/Cas9.

seven samples were injected Cre (ebv) Lox (helix loop helix) to the power 2000 bp of (A,G,U,C); In transcription & translation helicase gene editing of cis/trans 15Kbp of helix nucleotides and 80KBP of gene 7 nucleotides from 3'-ACCCAU -----3'-GGGGCCAUTC in 80 Kbp ebv (cis/trans) carbon and phosphate groups.

3- Isoform faverin drugs (typical compound) to disrupt GBM:-

The isomers cis/trans of C- & P- (Groups) in faverin drugs is included in six ribosomes of gene 7 of ebv; the matter that have been used is hydrogel injectable; the isoforms consist of trans/cis bantomers - helix loop helix power⁷² of nitrogenous base six ribosomes subunits of gene 7 of ebv and with bantomers of hydrogel they shape C- group and P-group loaded injectable hydrogel.

since injectable hydrogel is best form for therapy and treatments of brain tumors via helicase silicon based in its shape she performs 2 subunits of 6 ribosomes in helicase gene 7 of ebv; the Epstein Barr Virus immediate 200 and 6 bp units of protein dehydrogenase one cis and 2 trans of helicase protein base

17KD of adenine 3000KD of uracil 67KD of guanine and 78KD of cytosine.

4-Cis/trans isomers:-

the cis/trans form with helix loop helix based medullooblongata of Ahmad Issa Ahmad Funjan based nitrogenous base of DNA samples of CSF indicate that the cis/trans sample be in its shape is helix loop helix which could be benefits and suitable at the medical level; from this point we could invest DNA - helix loop helix of Medullooblongata of sir senior scientist Ahmad Issa Ahmad Funjan to get some (bp) of circulating DNA CSF samples since the nitrogenous bases consist from 7 molecules which are :-

1-5 dehydrogenase molecular system. 2-2 ebv molecules in sharing.

3-7 molecules of epidermal growth factors (beta,alpha,gamma) tumors necrosis factors. 4-seven bp of hydrogenous base - 6 molecules in its shape.

5-50 basic units of folic acids.

6-46,00 uniform of cis/trans Medullooblongata issue tissue Microarrays. 7-67,00 of nitrogenous - phosphate groups.

5- Medulloblastoma gene therapy:-

The MRI tools indicate that gene therapy is the most powerful procedure to treat medulloblastoma MRI- Imaging since we have some gene share in the same defect for brain tumors {different types of genes} like cAMP / wnt / shh.

These different types have the same crue cultures like wnt have the same criterias in organ tissue cultures like wnt have the same possibilities to mutate by human cytomegalovirus (hcmv) which will be mutated in GBM by the same effect.

the other organs like lung ; spleen; liver; pancreatic gland have the same percentage of (hcmv) titration and these organs present and appeared some percent risk factor when they tested by real time PCR -Seq

- Microchips like microarrays protein chips in its cancers.

6- DNA samples:-

ebv have the same powerful technology in its doing for diagnose and treat wnt medulloblastoma shh GBM and cAMP for Rhabdomyosarcoma; the best tool to test the percentage level of causing these tumors for human is protein -PCR human immunohistochemistry; the wnt indicate 60 level in its uniform; the shh is 30 level in its shape and finally cAMP best of top is 75% between all of these tumors

which are (MB,GBM & Rhabdomyosarcoma); the beauty form of ebv in its shape and helix loop helix based 2000 Kbp of genome and 70Kbp of it recycle; once we have engineered - modified with estrogen receptors hormone we can effective its ability to reinforce possibility in its Zig Zag structure.

the effect of eppendorf structural functions based 709¹⁰ phosphodiester bonds in Kwatt of its radiation with 25 basic units of helix loop helix in its complexity; the effect of radiation power of this uniform in ebv - shape is in its structure which can inject hydrogel inside tumor cells based tiny MRI Molecular imaging based on Tocagene shape & size in its loop.

ebv have some criterias which consist of 15K Dalton; 10 of same dalton of human cytomegalovirus (hcmv) which consist from 2000 bp of nucleotides that cause cancer for human like H.lymphoma and the same for (hcmv)that cause cancer for human like GBM in 30% in it consisting.

My medulla oblongata consists of 70% of hcmv and 20% of ebv which can act as a powerful tool to do cancer job therapy by ebv radiation and protein envelope of hcmv.

Since we can send a lot of tissue samples to university hospitals we can find the results and conclusion of these data.

3. RESULTS

The ebv have made a powerful tool engine in the life science for/to treat/therapy of brain tumors in different medical edgges (level) for some issue and results estimated inside our medical lab.

one of these method is injectable hydrogel with as based mentioned in previous idea; other treatment is by Tocagene; some of these tumors is fully treated via ebv {A study on Advanced Surgical Neuro Oncology} journal of molecular and genetic medicine and research publish journals- IJHS; for the weise issue i have been find that these results ignore everything of hcmv caused cancer cells inside human brain tumors like GBM & MB and forsure issue rhabdomyosarcoma.

Based on these issues I have to consider my work as a tool for 100% a therapy way and a clues job for a new drug world wide.

4. CONCLUSION

1-Tocagene

We previously showed that intracranial administration researchers of Toca 511 followed by 5-FC treatment resulted in long - term survival in intracranial tumor - bearing mice.

In the current study,we have demonstrated that comparable long - term sur-vival can also be achieved with Toca 511 delivered intravenously in the immune - competent mouse model.

These results further support a dual mechanism of action for combi-nation of Toca 511 and 5FC that involves both direct tumor chemoablation and consequent activation of an antitumor immune response.

In addition, no safety issues were observed in mice after intravenous administration of Toca 511; these findings were used to support this clinical trial phase- IV of intravenous delivery of Toca 511 followed by Toca FC in patients with recurrent high grade glioma.

2-hydrogel

new therapy approaches are required, and hydrogels proved to be a potential weapon against brain tumors.

Their unique characteristics, including high biocompatibility, biodegradability and response to stimuli, makes them excellent platforms for either localized and systemic drug delivery applications.

On one hand,injectable macroscopic hydrogels containing nanostructure DDS show a localized and controlled delivery of drug to the tumor, reduced toxicity in healthy tissues and an effective inhibition of tumor growth and recurrences.

On the other hand,to overcome the use of extremely invasive procedures, tailored nanogels became a very appealing strategy to efficiently deliver chemotherapeutic agents to neoplastic brain cells.

Combining both hydrogel and nanoparticle characteristics, they have successfully demonstrated the ability of crossing the BBB and suffering preferential uptake, thus identifying and killing tumor cells,without compromising healthy tissues.

Proof of concept demonstrations through invivo models are encouraging, although more studies are required to pave a successful IV Clinical trial.

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The two other clinical trials /2 articles in the supplement 1-gene therapy 2-surgery for heart and brain (tumors).

Conflict of interest statement none of the author have any conflict of interest

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